

MEDICAL SCIENCES

SURGICAL MANAGEMENT OF ABDOMINAL HERNIA IN CIRRHOTIC PATIENTS

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Abstract

In patients with liver cirrhosis, abdominal parietal hernias have a significantly higher prevalence than in the general population (20-40%), due to the presence of ascites, but also to a combination of factors that these patients are presenting: increased intra-abdominal pressure, weakness of muscle and of the fascial structures of the abdominal wall, on the background of poor nutrition, poor status and post-surgical scars.

The aim of our approach is to try to outline an optimal surgical protocol for the parietal defects of the cirrhotic, both from an ethical and strategic point of view, starting with the stage of cirrhosis or with the clinical presentation of the patients, taking into account our own experience, with the review data from the specialized literature.

In a retrospective study, the last 100 patients with liver cirrhosis operated in our clinic between 2015 and 2024 included 65 male and 35 female, aged between 45 and 70 years (on average 57 years).

The etiology of liver cirrhosis was represented by chronic ethanol consumption for 63 cases and viral infection (B or C) for 37 cases.

Laboratory data (albuminemia, bilirubinemia, prothrombin time) and clinical data (presence of ascites or encephalopathy) were used to classify cirrhosis in the Child-Pugh classification, and the information related to the type of hernia, the nature of the surgical indication (emergency or elective), the technique surgical procedure and postoperative evolution were collected from the observation sheets.

Analyzing our results, in accordance with those internationally achieved, some elements are defined to influence the results of hernia surgery in cirrhotic patients: the presence of ascites, the stage of cirrhosis evolution, the surgical technique used and the elective/emergency nature of the intervention.

The parietal defects of cirrhotic patients can be approached surgically with satisfactory results. The most effective are the scheduled interventions, performed in the compensated stages of cirrhosis.

The surgical technique uses both classical and alloplastic methods.

Conservative management is indicated in cases of uncomplicated hernia and in the decompensated stages of the disease.

Keywords: liver cirrhosis, abdominal parietal hernias, surgery

Introduction

In patients with liver cirrhosis, abdominal parietal hernias have a significantly higher prevalence than in the general population (20-40%), due to the presence of ascites, but also to a combination of factors that these patients are presenting: increased intra-abdominal pressure, weakness of muscle and of the fascial structures of the abdominal wall, on the background of poor nutrition, poor status and post-surgical scars. The precarious general status and systemic functional deficits, which accompany and aggravate the evolution of patients with liver cirrhosis, make the surgical approach to this group of patients, a subject of debate, considering the high rates of morbidity and mortality. In the case of a hernia, only the surgical intervention and the post-operative risk raise the mortality to 400% in cirrhotic patients than in non-cirrhotic patients.

On the other hand, the presence of the hernia alters the patient's quality of life, through local pain, with the limitation of physical activity. Delaying the operation involves the risk of complications - strangulation or ulceration, which will require immediate treatment and emergency surgical intervention in patients with liver cirrhosis, which also attracts an exponential increase of complications and of the mortality rate.

These are the controversies and dilemmas that persist in the operative approach to a parietal defect in the cirrhotic patient.

The aim of our approach is to try to outline an optimal surgical protocol for the parietal defects of the cirrhotic, both from an ethical and strategic point of view, starting with the stage of cirrhosis or with the clinical presentation of the patients, taking into account our own experience, with the review data from the specialized literature.

Material and methods

In a retrospective study, the last 100 patients with liver cirrhosis operated in our clinic between 2015 and 2024 included 65 male and 35 female, aged between 45 and 70 years (on average 57 years).

The etiology of liver cirrhosis was represented by chronic ethanol consumption for 63 cases and viral infection (B or C) for 37 cases.

Laboratory data (albuminemia, bilirubinemia, prothrombin time) and clinical data (presence of ascites or encephalopathy) were used to classify cirrhosis in the Child-Pugh classification, and the information related to the type of hernia, the nature of the surgical indication (emergency or elective), the technique surgical

procedure and postoperative evolution were collected from the observation sheets.

For cases of elective surgery, the preoperative preparation aimed at the biological optimization of the patient (correction of coagulation disorders, improvement of nutritional status and reduction of ascites volume). Emergency operations were indicated by complications (strangulation, incarceration, skin ulcerations, peritoneo-cutaneous fistulas, with ascetic fluid leakage).

The technique for solving parietal defects consisted of both classical techniques and alloplasties.

Regarding the Child-Pugh classification system, 37 patients were classified in grade A, 47 in grade B and 16 in grade C.

45 patients underwent elective surgery and 55 underwent emergency surgery, due to complications - incarceration in 20 cases, strangulation in 26 cases and ulceration in 9 cases.

50 cases presented umbilical hernia, 28 cases inguinal hernia, 16 cases postincisional hernia and 6 cases epigastric hernia.

Ascites was present in 33 patients. Of these, 19 were prepared preoperatively for the reduction of ascetic volume (hyposodium diet, diuretics, repeated paracentesis).

In 60 cases, the classic operative technique was applied. The decision was made, taking into account the clinical presentation of the hernia and the general condition of the patient. This solution was adopted in emergency interventions, for strangulation or ulceration of the skin, with a degree of contamination, but also for patients in the stages of decompensated cirrhosis. 40 cases were solved using alloplastic materials ("strengthening" polypropylene mesh): 21 umbilical hernias, 16 hernias, 3 inguinal hernias (Lichtenstein I technique). In 3 cases, segmental enterectomy with L-L anastomosis was necessary, due to irreversible injuries caused by intrasaccular strangulation.

The average hospitalization period was 10 days, with clear differences between the elective cases, in which the hospitalization was 5-10 days (on average 6 days) and those operated in emergency, whose hospitalization duration was 11-30 days (on average 14 days). The patients were surgically followed 30 days postoperatively. There were 57 postoperative complications - wound infections, seromas, hematomas; in 4 cases, wound dehiscence after the cure of the umbilical hernia, required reintervention.

The most severe complications - encephalopathy, aggravation/appearance of the ascites syndrome - ascites, liver failure and/or renal failure - occurred only in emergency operated patients.

The overall mortality rate was 20% - 11 deaths in Child C and 8 in Child B, one in Child A.

In the Child A class, the classic cure of the hernia was practiced in 11 cases and alloplasty in 18 cases.

24 interventions were performed for complicated hernias (incarceration 16 cases, strangulation 11 cases); 13 interventions were scheduled. One death was recorded in a patient with a strangulated umbilical hernia, in which a segmental enterectomy was also performed. Of the 12 postoperative complications recorded in this

group (5 wound infections, 3 hematomas and 4 seromas), 7 were in emergency operated cases. No hernia recurrences occurred.

For patients in the Child B stage, 30 surgeries were performed as an emergency and 17 scheduled. Alloplastic materials were used in 12 situations. Ascites was present in 21 cases, the scheduled cases benefited from preoperative preparation. Postoperatively, peritoneal drainage was not mounted in the presence of ascites, given the high risk of bacterial infection, which would have significantly increased the mortality rate.

Postoperative complications occurred in 24 cases, 16 of them operated in emergency, 8 after scheduled surgical interventions. The most serious complications (renal failure, encephalopathy and aggravation of the ascites syndrome) occurred in emergency operated patients. One case required surgical reintervention, due to postoperative wound dehiscence. There were 8 deaths in this group, but no relapses.

The patients in the Child C group underwent emergency surgery in 12 cases and scheduled in 4 cases, using only the classic technique. A high mortality rate was recorded - 11 (69%), all of which were operated under emergency conditions. Complications occurred in 3 cases, aggravated by encephalopathy (1 case) and liver failure (2 cases). No hernia recurrence was found in the postoperative follow-up period.

Discussions

Parietal defects are a frequent pathology in patients with liver cirrhosis, but the surgical approach of these patients still raises reservations, although operative failures have decreased in the last 50 years, due to diagnostic and therapeutic advances. Postoperative mortality decreased from 30% to 20%.

Analyzing our results, in accordance with those internationally achieved, some elements are defined to influence the results of hernia surgery in cirrhotic patients: the presence of ascites, the stage of cirrhosis evolution, the surgical technique used and the elective/emergency nature of the intervention.

The presence of ascites is most commonly associated with the presence of umbilical hernia in the cirrhotic patient. The increase in abdominal pressure, secondary to ascites, leads to the appearance of the hernia, together with the weakening of the musculo-fascial structures, on the background of insufficient nutrition. If the prevalence of umbilical hernia is 2% in the general population, in the context of cirrhosis with ascites, it increases to 20-40%. For other types of abdominal hernia, the presence of ascites does not directly influence the prevalence, leaving aside the other risk factors that cirrhotic patients develop. The volume and recurrence of ascites correlate positively with the prevalence of umbilical hernia, reaching 70% at the 3rd episode of ascites, but also with recurrence of the abdominal parietal defect. The rate of recurrent hernia in the presence of ascites reaches 45%. Adequate control of ascites (diuretics, hyposodium diet, iterative paracentesis, even transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt -TIPS, temporary peritoneal dialysis) significantly improves the results of surgical hernia treatment, in patients with cirrhosis, regarding postoperative complications - wound infection, infection, dehiscence of the wound, peritonitis and recurrence.

Emergency surgery, in the presence of ascites, imposed by complications (strangulation, peritonitis, skin fistula) is associated with a mortality of up to 20% and, at the same time, limits the technical possibilities of resolving the injury. In these circumstances, the use of alloplastic materials is contraindicated because of the very high septic risk.

Liver cirrhosis is a progressive chronic disease, characterized by the alteration of liver architecture and function. As the disease progresses, liver dysfunction leads to complex systemic dysfunctions. The cirrhotic patient may have kidney failure, cardio-pulmonary failure, diabetes, immunodeficiency, coagulation disorders, malnutrition. These correlated abnormalities set the stage for a difficult operation with unsatisfactory results. Postoperative complications can be related to the underlying disease (encephalopathy, aggravation of ascites syndrome, upper digestive hemorrhages, coagulopathies, hepatic-renal syndrome), but also general ones (acute respiratory distress syndrome, heart failure, myocardial ischemia), to which can be added those of the surgical wound (infection, dehiscence, bleeding).

The results of surgery in liver cirrhosis are correlated both with the stage of the disease and with the amplitude and duration of the operation, the average mortality rate varying from 8-25%. The stage of the disease is established using the Child-Pugh classification (ascites, encephalopathy), with reference to the MELD scale (serum albumin, serum bilirubin, creatinine, INR), which provides an objective assessment of the hepatic and renal function. The two scores, not mutually exclusive, are complementary and in the clinic it is more useful to calculate both.

For Child A patients with scheduled hernia operations, the results are encouraging, with minor postoperative complications (wounds, transient increase in azotemia, moderate reversible encephalopathy), a recurrence rate of about 8% and a mortality of 5%.

In hernia surgery, the long-term results show that the use of prostheses is a real, significant progress, but its implementation is still viewed with caution, considering the associated risks (intestinal occlusions, infections, adhesions, intestinal fistulas).

The laparoscopic approach brings a series of advantages for the cirrhotic patient: minimal incisions, which avoids venous dilations, minimal bleeding, reduction of electrolyte and protein losses, minimal postoperative pain, faster recovery and better absorption of ascites, compared to the open technique.

Emergency surgery in cirrhotic patients is followed by complications and a significantly higher mortality rate, compared to scheduled surgery. Emergency surgery was indicated in hernia complicated with ulceration, strangulation or incarceration. The duration of hospitalization and the severity of postoperative complications were also higher.

Complications that occur in cirrhotic patients after emergency hernia surgery in cirrhotic patients are related to the type of surgical intervention, the type of anesthesia and the evolutionary stage of the disease - insufficiency, hepatic, renal insufficiency, bleeding, portal encephalopathy and aggravation of the ascites syndrome.

Conclusions

The parietal defects of cirrhotic patients can be approached surgically with satisfactory results. The most effective are the scheduled interventions, performed in the compensated stages of cirrhosis.

The surgical technique uses both classical and alloplastic methods.

Conservative management is indicated in cases of uncomplicated hernia and in the decompensated stages of the disease.

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